

Characterising
Compton Thick AGN
and
AGN outflows
with
ATHENA

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(building on work by the Athena SWG2.2)

Athena Conference, Barcelona, 7-November-2022

Supported by the
European Union's
Horizon 2020 research
and innovation
programme under grant
agreement Number
101004168

Outline

- Science Working Group 2.2: Understanding the build-up of Super Massive Black Holes and Galaxies
- Why care?
- Work done on:
 - Capabilities of *Athena* for, and impact of PSF on, studies about:
 - Heavily obscured AGN
 - Ionised absorption in AGN
 - Ultra-Fast Outflows in QSO
- Summary

Why care?

- Most energy emitted from accretion in the Universe is obscured
 - From shape of CXB
- Relationship between build-up of SMBH and growth of host galaxies:
 - Through obscured phase $z \sim 1-4$

- **Unclear (but significant)** contribution of Compton Thick (CT) AGN
- One possible mechanism of direct influence of AGN on host galaxy: **outflows** (also radiation and jets, but another SWG)
 - **Warm absorbers** (WA): ionised gas seen in absorption in soft X-rays
 - **Ultra-Fast Outflows** (UFO): in hard X-rays at significant fractions of the speed of light

Topics covered

- *Athena* : wonderful capabilities
- At this stage: concentrating in (too?) simple requirements, uniform across topics
 - 10 objects/bin ($\sim 3\sigma$ detection)
 - 3-5 σ detection of individual spectral features
 - ...
- In SWG2.2: **concentrating in $z\sim 1-4$, $L_X\sim L^*$ and statistics of populations** (other SWG for $z <$ and $z >$), WFI spectroscopy from survey
 - Heavily obscured AGN: deep tier (SCIOBJ-221)
 - Ionised absorption in AGN: wide tier (SCIOBJ-222)
 - Ultra-Fast Outflows in QSO: wide tier (SCIOBJ-224) (X-IFU spcpy)
 - Detailed studies of individual sources, X-IFU spcpy: [Capri+22 XST-TN-028](#)

Methodology

- Latest results in [ASST-TN-0010_v2.1.pdf](#)
- Divide parameter space in bins (hyper-cubes):
 - $z, L_X, N_H, \xi, v_{\text{turbulence}}$...
- Survey geometry (several, actually...):
 - Wide tier: ... $249 \times 60\text{ks}$ or ... $117 \times 84\text{ks}$
 - Deep tier
- Analysis of (many) spectroscopic simulations to quantify:
 - Exposure time needed to get a given quality in a given parameter bin
 - Area/Exposure time needed to get a given number of sources
 - Impact of PSF (ASSATF): HEW=5 (as proposed), 8 (demonstrated), $10''$ (worst)

Heavily obscured (CT) AGN

$$\log N_{\text{H}}=24.5$$
$$L_{\text{X}}(2-10\text{keV})=5 \times 10^{44} \text{ cgs}$$
$$z=2$$

- Complete census of heavily obscured (dominant?) AGN
- Recovering L_{X} and N_{H} (CT: $\log(N_{\text{H}}/\text{cm}^{-2})=24.5, 25.5$) using only WFI spectrum and z
- Brightman&Nandra'11 torus
- Gilli+07 CXB model
- Including stray light
- Bayesian spectral fits (BXA Buchner+14)
- Optimising the survey geometry for this topic

Heavily obscured (CT) AGN

- Complete census of heavily obscured (dominant?) AGN
- Investigated only $L_x = 5 \times 10^{44}$ erg/s (L^*)

HEW (")	z=1,2,3	z=1,2,3,4
5	$\sim 17 \times 500\text{ks} \sim 8.0\text{Ms}$	$\sim 17 \times 1400\text{ks} \sim 23\text{Ms}$
8	$\sim 15 \times 700\text{ks} \sim 10.4\text{Ms}$	$\sim 17 \times 1800\text{ks} \sim 30.3\text{Ms}$
10	$\sim 2 \times 500\text{ks} + 12 \times 1000\text{ks} \sim 12.7\text{Ms}$	$\sim 27 \times 1200\text{ks} + 2 \times 2600\text{ks} \sim 38.0\text{Ms}$

- Can meet requirements even for HEW=10" for z=1,2,3 and moderately CT AGN in reasonably sized deep survey tier
- Considerable uncertainty on XLF and dependence on bin definition

Current work on AGN census

- Approach above ~OK for feasibility studies
- But real need is to tell apart different evolution models for CT AGN
- Working on it (G. Mountrichas, A. Georgakakis):
 1. Assume XLF Ueda+14 and survey geometry:
 - a. Simple parameterisation of CT contribution
 2. Get model through the *Athena* mirror and WFI
 3. Spectral analysis of the sources: $\{z, N_H, L_X\}$ distributions for each source
 4. Bayesian fit XLF to the simulated sources
 - a. Compare best fit XLF with input one
 - b. How different XLF have to be to tell them apart?
- Aim is to finish by end 2022

Ionised absorption in AGN

- Determine incidence of strong and ionised absorbers (WA) in general population of AGN
- Provide targets for detailed X-IFU studies
- Recovering within 50% $\log \xi$ (2-4) and $N_{\text{H,ion}}$ ($\log(N_{\text{H,ion}}/\text{cm}^{-2})=22-24$) **using only WFI spectrum**
- Ueda+03 XLF, 40% WA (Blustin+05)
- Using wide ($249 \times 60\text{ks}$) tier of survey

Credit: A. Georgakakis

Ionised absorption in AGN

Credit: A. Georgakakis

- Can meet requirements for L^* even for $\text{HEW}=10''$ for $z=1,2,3$
- Impact of lower angular resolution marginal

Ionised absorption in AGN

$\log L_x = 44.5$

10 arcsec

8 arcsec

5 arcsec

- Can meet requirements for L^* even for HEW=10" for $z=1,2,3$
- Impact of lower angular resolution marginal

expected number of WA in Athena/WFI surveys

Ultra-Fast Outflows in QSO

- Determine incidence, duty cycle and energetics of UFOs
- Detecting FeXXV and FeXXVI 6.7-6.9keV features at $>3\sigma$ using only WFI spectrum
- $\log \xi = 4$, $\log(N_{\text{H,ion}}/\text{cm}^{-2}) = 24$, $v_{\text{turb}} = 3000$ km/s, $v_{\text{out}} = 0.1c$ Luminari+18
 - Xstar model Lanzuisi+12
- Ueda+03 XLF, 30% UFO (Tombesi+10)
- Using wide (117 \times 84ks) tier of survey: transient
- Investigating the effect of different assumptions on physical pars.

Credit: G. Lanzuisi

Ultra-Fast Outflows in QSO

Credit: L. Zappacosta

- Can meet requirements for L^* even for HEW=10" for $z=1,2,3,4$
- Impact of lower angular resolution marginal
- Much stronger dependence on v , N_{H} (-40-50%) and rel. effects (\sim -60%)

Ultra-Fast Outflows in QSO

$\log L_x = 44.5$

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X-ray spectroscopic z

- Previous works using spectral fits promising (e.g. Simmonds+18)
- Initially using method of Castelló+11, essentially:
 - Analysis of ratio between spectrum and simple model (or $\Delta\chi^2$), to look for peaks of emission
 - Spectral line fit with peak energy as initial input (FeK α 6.4keV)
 - Preliminary tests with simulated CT AGN spectra: $\sim 90\%$ redshift recovered $\leq 1\sigma$ for $L_x \geq 5 \times 10^{45}$ erg/s for $T_{\text{exp}} \geq 840$ ks at $z=1-4$
- Current work (see V.P. Koushika's poster):
 - uxclumpy models representative of local Sy1 and 2 (including CT)
 - $z=1,2,3,4$, $\log(N_{\text{H}}/\text{cm}^{-2})=22-26$, $L_x=10^{44-45}$ erg/s
 - Noise reduction, continuum modelling and feature detection using wavelets

Summary

- *Athena* wonderful machine
- SWG2.2: Understanding the Build-up of SMBH and Galaxies
 - Relevant for assembly and evolution of galaxies
- Method
 - Requirements (simple): concentrating in $z \sim 1-4$ and around $L_X \sim L^*$
 - Spectroscopic simulations and analysis
 - Statistics of populations
 - Investigating effect of PSF
- Different aspects: WFI survey
 - Complete census of heavily obscured AGN: deep
 - Up to $z=3$ even in worst PSF
 - Working on more sophisticated treatment
 - Determine incidence of warm absorbers in AGN: wide
 - Up to $z=3$, limited impact of different PSF
 - Determine incidence, duty cycle and energetics of UFOs: wide
 - Up to $z=4$, limited impact of different PSF
 - Stronger dependence on assumed physical parameters and modelling